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Summary

Tyschenko S.V. Agricultural Green Tourism Development on the Territory of the Zhytomyr Region.

The process of formation of rural green tourism in Zhytomyr region is considered. The crisis situation in the agrarian sector of the economy has led to a new form of economy – entrepreneurship of rural green tourism. The general physical and geographical characteristics of the region are carried out. It is proved that the region has a favorable physical-geographical and economic-geographical position, which contributes to its compact population, high level of economic development of the territory, creates preconditions for life activities of people, especially in rural areas – the establishment of rural green tourism. Rural areas of Zhytomyr region have a very interesting ethno-cultural resource base, historical and archaeological sites, a very rich natural and climatic basis for the development of rural tourism. The mild climate, picturesque landscapes, the most interesting historical and cultural heritage, original crafts and crafts are the base for various types of tourism in the countryside. At present, steps are being taken by the state to support the development of rural tourism.

Keywords: rural green tourism, rural territory, recreation, peasants, countryside, farmstead of rural green tourism, rest, agriculture, production of agricultural products.

UDC 911.2-502.7.58

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INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE CONSERVATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENVIRONMENT: A GEOGRAPHIC APPROACH

Tourism is always embracing economy, social and environmental impacts. For this reason, the policy of sustainable development of tourism is necessary. The general approach is that gov-

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Article Info: Received: September 18, 2017;
Final revision: April 6, 2018; Accepted: April 14, 2018.

ernments have paid attention to tourism ecologically in the long run. This is approved and financially self-sufficient, and from the perspective of social and moral for local communities is beneficial and promising. The aim of this study is to evaluate the effects of wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas. The purpose of applied research and in terms of data collection is descriptive and analytical. The study population consists of 3 villages' khawmirabad rural district, Sarkol Zarivar which in the whole 93 villages of this area, a number of villages was selected. Sample households of the village and randomly classified and 12 villages were selected. Cochran formula used to determine the sample size and questionnaire to 330 randomly selected villages were selected among heads of households. The validity of the test Cronbach's alpha was 0.77 percent. For statistical analysis of data from one sample -t- test, chi-square test and ANOVA test in spss software is used. The results show that tourism in economic and socio-cultural aspects have a positive impact on the conservation and sustainable development of the environment.

Key words: environment, conservation, sustainable development, geographic approach, tourism.

Introduction. In the present era of tourism, the tourism economy is becoming one of the fastest growth industries in the world, a tool for the creation of national income and one of the main pillars of the global economy; also, of concepts, forms of development considered¹. Natural tourism activity is a complex with other sectors of society and the economy, having in common the effects and consequences of different which should be in the process of planning all its aspects considered the take up of negative factors and threat prevention and the effects of economic, social and environmental aspects related to the increase². Tourism and environment are mutually dependent. Thus, development and management of tourism so that the environment is a key factor in achieving sustainable development is taken into account³. Tourists need to be part of the natural, cultural and human environment, to maintaining the balance between them⁴, because the vast majority of recreational activities directly depends on natural resources in the destination⁵; the negative environmental impact of tourism including air pollution, soil pollution, water pollution, traffic congestion problems, poured spraying waste, damage to historical buildings, destruction of natural herbs, destruction of wildlife, etc.⁶

Wetlands are beautiful sights. It is necessary the tourism industry to develop properly planned and managed, as a creator or drive the development process to

¹ N. Rattanasuwongchai (1998): *Rural Tourism: The Impact on Rural Communities*. Thailand Food and Fertilizer Technology Center.

² T.K. Reinhold and A. Diara (2000). "The role of tourism in development planning". Department of Business Management.

³ World Tourism Organization 1379, "National and regional tourism planning". Translated by M.A. Zadeh. Tehran: Cultural Research Bureau, p.73.

⁴ M. Altinay, K. Hussain (2005). "Sustainable Tourism Development: A Case Study of North Cyprus". *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Volume 17, Issue 3, p.274.

⁵ Sara Dolnicar, Friedrich Leisch (2008). "Selective Marketing for Environmentally Sustainable Tourism". *Tourism Management*, Volume 29, Issue 4, p.672.

⁶ M. Altinay, K. Hussain, *op.cit.*, p.277.

achieve sustainable development in the local communities and aquatic ecosystems and wetlands.

Wetlands of inertia relative water have been developed among many ecosystems production in the world, comparable to rain forests and coral reefs, which include a variety of species of microorganisms, plants, insects, amphibians, reptiles, birds, fish and mammals¹. The regeneration of these natural ecosystems engages the restoration of natural materials and rustic design of the most important research areas and many of the country's executive. The aim of this study is to evaluate the effects of wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas surrounding the Zarivar, located in the city of Marivan.

Theoretical framework. Tourism, as an important form of human activities, has an important impact. The effects in the region of tourism destination interact with the local environment, economy, culture and society is evident. Also, a large part of the activities of tourism planning is done on the effects of tourism². The effects of tourism development, the complex process of change and exchange between tourists and destination host settlements are included³.

The environmental dimension of tourism, one of the favorite areas of geographers, is the reason for the implication of geography with a robust approach in the field of human relations and the environment⁴. The analysis of tourism on the environment and resources is an area in which natural and human geographers study problems related to tourism.

Lagoon refers to a place where water is the main factor for the environment, plants and animals, all areas, rivers, lakes, littoral, mangrove forest, hatcheries, channels, etc. where the maximum water depth of more than 3 meters during low tide are not applicable. The need for environmental protection and utilization of natural resources, including sustainable development is a necessity. Park managers, protected areas and wetlands face many decisions that need to be appropriately adopted.

Cover and dynamic monitoring of land use and landscape in protected areas and wetlands need to understand how they effect on nature; the process of reconstruction and rehabilitation and that of protection on long term are very important.

Wetlands are some of the most important ecosystems on Earth. Safe areas for wildlife in these areas are, however, threatened. Wetlands through water are biologically the most diverse ecosystems of the Earth. They have spread across the world and play an important role in the water cycle, control the regional floods, prevent ero-

¹ Nejma Danielle Piagentini (2006). *The Science and Policy that Compels the Wetland Mitigation of Phosphate-Mined Lands*. Master of Science Thesis, University of South Florida, p.1.

² Peter Mason (2003). *Tourism Impacts, Planning and Management*. Jordan Hill: Routledge, p.10.

³ Y. Yoon (2002). *Development of a Structural Model for Tourism Destination Competitiveness from Stakeholders, Perspectives*. PhD Thesis. Virgin Polytechnic Institute State University, p.14.

⁴ Lisle S. Mitchell, Peter E. Murphy (1991). "Geography and tourism". *Annals of Tourism Research*, Volume 18, Issue 1, p. 57.

sion, water treatment and recirculation of nutrients. They also are transitional zones between land and water environments and, as resources, they become attractive. Negative human activities greatly affect the wetland ecosystem¹.

Fig. 1. Connections among wetland functions, uses and values. Source: K.T. Turner (2000)²

¹ William J. Mitsch and James G. Gosselink (2000). *Wetlands*. Third edition. New York: John Wiley & Sons

² K.T. Turner, J. Bergh, T. Barendregt, J. Straaten and E. Maltby (2000). "Ecological-economic analysis of wetlands: scientific integration for management and policy". *Ecological Economics*, Volume 35, Issue 1: 7–23.

Human impacts on wetlands can include physical changes, such as deposition and changes in water flow; also, general biological changes such as loss of biodiversity, the introduction of invasive species and changes in the structure of society¹.

Table 1.a

National studies in the field of research

Writer(s)	Subject	Results
Hassan Ismail-Zadeh et al. (2015)	Sustainable tourism in wetlands ecosystem (case study: lagoon city cash)	Results show that a total of 33 variables measuring institutional economics, social, cultural and ecological environmental study sustainable tourism in wetland ecosystems, 3 variables from the perspective of the people and every 33 variables, from the perspective of the authorities about have been confirmed. However, the analysis of two views converge (consistency) in the 3-variable divergence (anisotropy) has been observed in five variables.
Danehkar et al (2012)	Designed to nature-based tourism in the wetland using Spatial Multi Criteria Evaluation (SMCE)	According to the results of the implementation of a hierarchical approach in prioritizing the main criteria tourism, landscape criteria with the highest weighting coefficient allocated to the first priority. With regard to border the lagoon on the development of aquatic plants in the end zone three weights recreation including ecotourism, nature based tourism without physical development and physical development of nature-based tourism in the chaghakhur wetland identification and location.
Saman Gulali Zadeh (2013)	The effect of different methods of natural ecosystems tourism on the parameters of environmental education	Participation in the Environmental Education considerable increases knowledge and considerable changes in their attitudes and behavior. The results show that the difference between the two groups of the tips mentioned in this study influence the environmental education.
Narges Vazin (2014)	Develop a model for strategic planning of wetland ecotourism towards wetland ecosystem health and sustainable development of rural communities, the range wetlands Miyankaleh	The results show the capacity of ecotourism wetlands was high in the studied area, the capacity of ecotourism based on the Likert scale in most parameters determined optimal level of numerical control (number 3) is evaluated and alpha level of 0.05 was significant.
Sajad Astani (2013)	Zoning and Wetlands International Tourism Climate Assessment Shadegan using geographic information system and single model	Results indicate that the Tourism Climate Index in April in the northern part of the lagoon Yahoo Messenger has good conditions in the central and southern part an excellent rating. The total wetland area in March compared to the other months of the year shows that the situation is more favorable.

¹ John A. Freeland and Jim L. Richardson (1997). *Soils and Sediments as Indicators of Agricultural Impacts on Northern Prairie Wetlands*. In: S.A. Peterson, L. Carpenter, G. Guntenspergen and L.M. Cowardin (eds.), *Pilot Test of Wetland Condition Indicators in the Prairie Pothole Region of the United States*. Washington DC: US Environmental Protection Agency.

Hosein Negaresh (2013)	The feasibility of developing tourism Poldokhtar wetlands based on SWOT analysis	The results showed, for the study area, 21 internal strengths. And external opportunities as regional advantages and weaknesses internal and external threats as bottlenecks 22 feasibility of developing tourism in the region. Conclusion: the threshold of the high vulnerability of wetlands for tourism, which requires review and appropriate politics.
Mohsen Ranjbar et al (2011)	Anzali Lagoon role in sustainable tourism development and sustainable planning	City Bandar Anzali most points demographic adjacent wetland is a wetland with an approximate length of 33 km and a width of 18 km from the north to the city of Bandar Anzali and the Caspian Sea, east to the village of Hasan River, from West to villages shoots ration of the Ali Abad Kaporchal and from the south Handekhale villages and Nokhaleh ends. Proximity to the major cities of Rasht, Anzali, Someye sara roads, as well as a lot of it in terms of tourism has become one of the country's major hubs. Every year a large number of tourists nationwide during the holiday season, especially in spring and summer, travel to the area.

Source: Findings, 2017

Methodology. The purpose of this study in terms of data collection is descriptive and analytical. Data collection in the theoretical part of the documentary and in the field of survey based on interviews and questionnaires were used. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas. The study population consists of villages 3 khawmirabad rural district, Sarkol and zarivar which of the 93 villages of this area, a number of villages were selected. Sample households of the village and randomly classified and 12 villages were selected.

In field studies, collecting required data, preparing questionnaire and getting interviews between the villages were the most important part. A questionnaire was designed including household questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of closed questions. In designing questions, the Likert scale was used. The validity of the test Cronbach's alpha was 0.77 percent. For statistical analysis of data from one sample t test, chi-square test and ANOVA test in spss software were used.

Research area. Lagoon flows 3 km West Marivan in Kurdistan province and the tourist attractions of the province. Sweet pond water is boiling and is funded from a number of source floors. In winter the lake freezes completely. The wetlands in longitude '8 ° 46 latitude '32 ° 35 and the height of 1285 meters above sea level is located. During Zarivar Lake about 5 km and a width of about 1.6 km. The extent of wetlands because of changes in the volume of water in different seasons changing and the maximum depth of 5.5 meters. The lagoon's largest and most beautiful fresh

water lake west of Iran and one of the most unique freshwater lake in the world and all circumstances considered a wetland of international development.

Table 1.b

International studies in the field of research

Writer(s)	Subject	Results
Hailun et al.	Lake Wetland Management System Case Study wetland ecotourism compatibility with Jin Yan	Wetland ecotourism sustainable development must rely on the support of local community residents and community involvement of local communities as an important part of the wetland ecotourism management. It must be said that in addition to evaluating the ecological natural phenomenon, the conditions of local communities in all aspects, including capacity development of eco-tourism, financial strength, attitude and understanding of local communities can contribute a prerequisite for the successful implementation of ecotourism.
SONG et al.	The effects on tourism and sustainable development of regional wetland Ning Guy	A unique wetland ecosystem of rich biodiversity, functioning and values of environmental, economic and social lot. Cultural specificity / cultural heritage and biodiversity of wetland ecosystems have added value. Wetlands having unique natural and cultural landscape are appropriate for ecotourism development.
Dong	Check the status of the development of tourism and protection of wetland resources in Dongting Lake	In summary, managing wetland tourism can realize economic development, tourism, and yet can support wetland ecological conservation.
Lili et al.	A preliminary study on tourist behavior in a pond	The kinds of wetland ecosystem services, tourism and science education are very important functions, and wetland ecotourism, and tourism training and new exploitation of wetland resources are applicable.
Liu et al.	Case study analyzes the effects of ecotourism on Sustainable Development Lagoon Jin Yan	Lagoon wetland ecotourism is based on natural resources. In fact, ecotourism wetlands include wetland ecological culture, which is ethical and responsible ecotourism characteristics of wetlands; wetland protection into account and sustainable development of wetlands protection.
Wang	Study the development of tourism and wetland ecosystems	Because of its wetlands rich in biodiversity and cultural diversity, value and function of environmental education tourism is responsible travel to natural environments that protect the environment, and the economy helps Aboriginal people. Especially in sensitive and protected areas to reduce the negative environmental effects caused by the operation will be balanced environment.

Source: Findings, 2017

Table 2

Sample villages and distributed questionnaires among them

Rural district	The name of the village	The number of households	Total population	The number of questionnaires
Zarivar	Kani kabod	41	181	7
	Siyanav	196	845	33
	Kani Sanan	171	660	28
	Dara tefey	244	924	41
	ney	656	2560	55
Khawmirabad	Savjey	280	1152	44
	Anjiran	111	455	22
	Yangijeh	90	362	17
Sarkol	Balek	139	529	24
	Darziyan	112	451	21
	Sharani	113	472	23
	marg	89	365	15
Total	12	41	8956	330

Source: Findings, 2017

Approximate size pond water is about 30 million cubic meters. Wetland about 22, 5 km and the average rainfall is 786 mm per year. Relative humidity equal to 4/58 percent and average annual evaporation of 1900 mm has been reported (Environmental Protection Agency, 1393). Villages of 200 meters to 3 kilometers lagoon flows have been chosen. The main activity is agriculture and horticulture villages and, in some cases, the work in border markets. Despite the economic situation and the Lake tourists in the villages around, the wetlands have been affected.

Descriptive findings. Check the individual characteristics of the respondents indicate that all respondents were male, 15.1% of respondents aged 25-15 years in terms of age, 33.5% of respondents aged 35-25 years, 30.3% of respondents age 45-35 years, 16.1% of respondents aged 55-45 years and 5.0% in those aged over 55 years have been. In terms of education, 1.8 percent illiterate, 20.6% of subjects at the elementary level, 28.9 percent of people in the middle, 27.1 percent of high school and 21.6 percent of those in upper secondary level. Nearly 80 percent of people have their home at his residence. Job status among respondents are 37.2% of agricultural jobs, 20.2% of public service jobs (shops, taxi driver between rural-urban), 5.5% of government employees, 14.2% of self-employed workers and 22.5% of other work.

Fig. 2. Location of the study area

In this study in the context of assessing the impact of tourism in maintaining wetland ecosystem and environmental sustainability in rural areas, 27 indicators defined and each of these indicators in SPSS studied and analyzed, which results in Table 6 have been shown. In the table the consent of respondents to each indicator, average and chi-square are studied. In the field of ecological and environmental dimensions, 15 indicators (diversity of flora and fauna, water resources management, agricultural waste management, organic farming, water pollution lake, nature conservation and biodiversity, the pollution of the environment, increase women's participation in the protection of ecosystems use of construction materials good, picked allow water from the wetland and watershed wetlands, lack of wastewater management alternatives, the harm to the animals wetlands) wildlife (land use changes as a result of

tourism activities) used according the optimal numerical test (3), the average on most parameters to measure the low post favorable than assessed value and alpha level of 0.00 were significant.

Table 3

The individual characteristics of respondents in rural areas, border areas

Individual characteristics of respondents			
Index	Classification	Frequency	Percent
Age	15 - 25	1338	100
	25-35	0	0
	35-45	33	15.1
	45-55	73	33.5
	55 >	66	30.3
Level of education	Illiterate	35	16.1
	Primary	11	5.0
	Guidance	4	1.8
	High school	45	20.6
	High school graduate or higher	63	28.9
Main job	Farmer	59	27.1
	Public services	47	21.6
	Government's employee	173	79.4
	Working	20	9.2
	Dehyaran	25	11.5
	Other	81	37.2
Job Satisfaction	Too much	44	20.2
	A lot	12	5.5
	So much for	31	14.2
	Little	49	22.5
	Very little	1338	100

Source: Findings, 2017

Table 5

Dimensions and indicators measured in this study

Dimension	Criteria
Ecological-environmental	Diversity of flora and fauna, water resources management, management of wastewater agriculture, organic farming, water pollution lake, nature conservation and biodiversity, the pollution of the environment, increase public participation in protecting ecosystems, use of building materials suitable for harvesting allowed water from the wetland and watershed wetlands, lack of wastewater management alternatives, the harm to the animals wetlands) wildlife (land use changes as a result of tourism activities, shortage of farm and garden organ in the villages of the region, consuming large amounts of fertilizer and pesticides Chemicals in food production.
Economic	Transport facilities, access to weekly markets, poor access to employment opportunities in the area, lack of eco-cottage industries in rural areas, rural women's employment, increase the purchasing power of the local community.
Sociocultural	Recognition of the environment, the awareness of people about the connection between the village and the region, people's belief in wetland conservation as cultural heritage, lack of opportunities for public participation in decision-making and programs for the protection of wetlands, Development Education environmental learning, sense of cooperation in tourism development and maintenance of wetland ecosystems.

Source: Findings, 2017.

Table 6

Evaluation of the effects of wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas of the respondents. Source: Findings, 2017

Dimension	Variables	Too much	Much	Some what	Little	Very little	Average	Chi-square	Sig
Ecological-Environmental	Diversity of flora and fauna	18.70	14.00	12.50	24.00	30.80	2.32	36.555	.000
	water resource management	15.30	19.30	18.10	24.30	23.10	2.21	8.735	.000
	Agricultural waste management	21.80	14.00	16.50	23.70	24.00	2.10	12.941	.000
	Organic farming	31.80	15.90	23.40	5.60	23.40	3.51	61.850	.000
	Reducing water pollution in the lake	15.30	6.50	26.50	20.60	31.20	2.56	59.421	.000
	Conservation of Nature and Biodiversity	20.20	11.80	16.50	25.90	25.50	2.85	23.097	.000
	Reduce the pollution of the environment	12.10	4.00	18.70	27.70	37.40	2.73	109.078	.000
	Increase women's participation in the protection of ecosystems	20.60	29.90	17.80	19.60	12.10	3.27	26.523	.000
	The use of appropriate building materials	10.30	19.90	24.90	28.70	16.20	2.32	33.408	.000
	Allowed to withdraw water from the pond	39.60	32.40	11.80	6.20	10.00	3.82	143.377	.000
	Alternative Wastewater Management System	16.20	16.80	19.60	22.40	24.90	2.60	8.798	.000
	The damage to wetland animals	4.70	9.00	28.30	35.50	22.40	2.99	107.769	.000
	Land use change as a result of tourism activities	17.10	22.70	12.50	23.10	23.70	3.12	16.274	.000
	Organic farms & gardens in rural area	20.20	7.80	26.20	20.20	25.50	3.70	34.997	.008
Fertilizer and chemical pesticides in agriculture	19.60	26.50	22.40	17.40	14.00	3.86	14.498	.006	
Economic	Transport facilities	24.00	34.00	20.90	16.20	5.00	3.44	72.442	.001
	Weekly market access	23.10	30.20	18.40	18.10	10.30	3.48	104.218	.000
	Access to employment opportunities in the area	19.30	5.60	13.40	29.00	32.70	2.50	153.938	.000
	Eco cottage industries in villages	16.20	17.40	15.30	25.90	25.20	2.50	182.598	.000
	Employment for rural women	17.3	23.5	20.0	29.4	9.8	3.82	27.098	.000
	Increase the purchasing power of the local community	12.2	12.2						
Social and cultural	Recognizing the environmental area	11.8	38.4	33.3	3.25	113.843	.000		
	Awareness of the linkage between the village and the region	20.90	25.20	22.10	18.40	13.40	3.86	12.660	.000
	People believed to protect the wetlands as cultural heritage	14.30	14.03	24.60	26.80	19.90	2.83	21.134	.000
	Public participation in decision-making and wetland conservation programs	29.30	37.40	13.70	11.20	8.40	3.68	102.629	.000
	Development of environmental education and learning	13.10	19.60	17.80	28.70	20.90	2.25	20.667	.000
	Sense of cooperation in tourism development and maintenance of wetland ecosystems	20.0	34.5	22.7	13.3	9.4	3.58	47.765	.000

One of the main factors in more evaluations performed on the development of tourism in local communities has been emphasized, the economic effects of tourism. Tourism in recent years as a very important economic factor is of great concern; as well as all the places where the tourism industry will need to develop appropriate tourism professionals and executive management.

The economic dimension in the study 6 index (transport facilities, access to weekly markets, poor access to employment opportunities in the area, lack of rural industries compatible with the environment in rural areas, employment of rural women, increase the purchasing power of the local community) have been used according to the mean square of each indicator; tourism had a positive effect on the economic situation of the rural areas of wetland ecosystems. Programs for wetland protection, development of environmental education and learning, sense of cooperation in tourism development and maintenance of wetland ecosystems have been used; according to the index that the social dimension of cultural tourism in rural areas of wetland ecosystems have a positive impact.

Table 7

The test results T wetland ecosystem conservation and sustainable environment impact of tourism in rural areas

Index	Mean Difference	Standard deviation	Index T	Sig	Confidence Interval 95% of the Difference	
					Upper	Low
Ecological-environmental	2.1169	1.209	0.007	46306	-.3000	-.1139
Economic	3.8131	4.374	.000	.89774	0.0106	0.0444
Social and cultural	3.2764	1.479-	0.003	31268	0.0326	0.0046

Source: Findings, 2017

Table 8

The analysis of the impact of wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas

Index		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Ecological-environmental	Between Groups	27.814	22	23.907	24.367	.000
	Within Groups	260.461	357	.730		
	Total	268.275	359			
Economic	Between Groups	15.517	2		10.318	.000
	Within Groups	244.865	357	7.759		
	Total	260.383	359	.686		
Social and cultural	Between Groups	.826	2		653.	.000
	Within Groups	277.507	357	6.543		
	Total	278.333	359	.777		

Source: Findings, 2017

In one sample T-test number 3 as desirable numerical or theoretical middle test is intended. If the lower and upper limits are positive posts will be larger than the observed value. And when both are negative numerical average calculated from the theoretical middle or utility of the test and show less favorable conditions is not. The

analysis shows that the level of tourism in economic and socio-cultural aspects has a positive impact on the wetland ecosystem conservation and sustainable environment in rural areas.

To explain whether the environmental factors of ecological, economic, social and cultural tourism in the wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability in rural areas have a significant difference or not, the one-way analysis of variance was used. According to the results, Table 8 and the significance level (0.000) can be said that to amount F for the impact of tourism on wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability in rural areas has been significant. In other words, this value indicates that at least there is a significant difference between the two; to check the claim of pair wise comparisons (Tukey) was used in the Table 9.

Table 9

ANOVA multiple comparisons test

Exam type	Index	Rural	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	.Sig	Confidence Interv 95%	
						Upper Bound	Lower Bound
Tukey	Ecological-environmental	Economic	.32389	.10066	.000	-.0770	-.5508
			.00526	.12733	.000	.2941	-.3052
		Social and cultural	-.32389	.10066	.001	.5508	.0770
			.33833	.13505	.001	.6262	-.0095
	Economic	Near	-.11944	.09760	.000	.3492	-.1103
			.58611	.12346	.000	.8767	.2955
		Middle	.11944	.09760	.001	.1103	-.3492
			.46667	.13095	.000	.7749	.1585
	Social and cultural	Near	-.10236	.10391	.000	.1390	-.3501
			-.06389	.13143	.001	.2454	-.3732
		Middle	.10236	.10391	.001	.3501	-.1390
			.04267	.13940	.001	.3698	-.2864

Source: Findings, 2017

Meanwhile, the Kruskal-Wallis test results also show that the alpha level of 0.001 significant wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental impact of tourism in rural areas is sustainable. As the ratings show that an average rural flows to the highest allocated, that may be because it flows near the villages of the district wetland ecosystem in the region: by consequence, the impacts (positive and negative) of tourism on the ecosystem in the villages.

Results. Development of tourism in an area with tourist arrivals continue to change the landscape of human and natural, socio-cultural changes, economic and

environmental ecology. Tourism needs to provide recreation areas for tourists and create jobs and income for residents of local communities without damaging the environment, local communities and natural ecosystems. The wetland ecosystems, due to the wide range of ecological attractions and unique natural and cultural landscape, are highly regarded. The results show that tourism in economic and socio-cultural aspects have a positive impact on the wetland ecosystem conservation and sustainable rural environment. But there are also some negative effects on the environment and the stable wetland ecosystems. The findings of the Kruskal-Wallis test show that tourism in villages near the wetland ecosystem Zarivar (Yangijeh, dara tefey, Siyanav, kani kabod, Kani Sanan and ney) is the most affected by the economic dimension of the rural areas. Also, there is a negative impact on the region in the field of the environment (pollution of the lake water, lack of protection of nature and biodiversity, environment pollution, harm to animals, etc.).

Table 10

Effect relationship between the villages’ wetland ecosystem conservation and environmental sustainability of tourism in rural areas Kruskal-Wallis test

	Rural district	Count	Average ratings
Impact of tourism in wetland ecosystem conservation and sustainable environment	Khaw and Mirabad	83	163.46
	Zarivar	96	199.36
	Srkl	151	154.17
	Total	330	
	Df	2	
	Sig	0.001	

Source: Findings, 2017

Suggestions.

1. Breach planning and proper management to prevent water pollution and protect the environment and surrounding wetland ecosystem around the Lake.
2. Encourage people to protect nature and the ecosystem around the lagoon and also avoid harming wildlife wetland ecosystems.
3. Provision of infrastructure and services needed by tourists and locals
4. Proper management of water resources and water are allowed harvesting of wetland for tourists and locals.
5. Alternative wastewater management systems for rural areas, especially rural areas around the wetland ecosystem.
6. Avoid the use of fertilizers and chemical pesticides in agriculture and horticulture.
7. Learning and teaching people to understand the environment and the necessity to protect wetlands as cultural heritage.

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Резюме

Джафарі М. Дослідження ролі туризму у збереженні та сталому розвитку довкілля: географічний підхід.

Туризм завжди має економічні, соціальні та екологічні наслідки, виходячи з чого необхідною є політика сталого розвитку туризму. Загальний підхід полягає в тому, що уряди постійно звертають увагу на екологічний туризм. Це явище схвалене і фінансово самодостатнє, а з соціальної та моральної точок зору є корисним і перспективним для місцевих громад. Метою даного дослідження є оцінка впливів туризму на екосистем водно-болотних угідь, що охороняються, та екологічну стійкість сільської місцевості. З точки зору прикладних досліджень та збору даних, мета даної статті має описовий та аналітичний характер. Територія дослідження включає поселення Хаммірабадського сільського району місцевості Сарколь Зарівар, яка в цілому включає 93 поселення, з котрих і було обрано певну кількість сіл. Окремі домогосподарства були класифіковані з подальшим вибором 12 сіл. Для визначення розміру вибірки і кількості запитань у анкеті, яка охопила 330 керівників домогосподарств, було використано формулу Кокрана. Дійсність альфа тесту Кронбаха становила 0,77%. Для статистичного аналізу даних кожного елемента вибірки, який було проведено у комп'ютерній програмі SPSS, застосовано критерій χ^2 -квадрат і тест ANOVA. Результати показують, що туризм в економічному та соціокультурному плані позитивно впливає на збереження та сталий розвиток навколишнього середовища.

Ключові слова: довкілля, збереження природи, сталий розвиток, географічний підхід, туризм.